

**THE ISSUE OF ATTITUDE TO ZAHIRIDDIN BABUR'S
PERSONALITY IN THE NOVEL "RAIDERS FROM THE NORTH"**

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Abstract. *This thesis examines the novel "Raiders from the North" by Alex Rutherford, one of the famous English writers. This novel is the first book of the epic novel "Moghul Empire". This work is dedicated to the life and experiences of Zahiriddin Babur Mirza. By studying this work, we tried to determine how the personality of Babur Mirza was presented in the eyes of English writers.*

Keywords: *Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, Amir Temur, Humayun Mirza, Shaybani Khan, Khanzodabegim, Samarkand, India, epic novel.*

**"RAIDERS FROM THE NORTH" ROMANIDA ZAHIRIDDIN BOBUR
SHAXSIGA MUNOSABAT MASALASI**

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Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tezisdan mashhur ingliz yozuvchilaridan bo'lgan Alex Rutherfordning "Raiders from the North" romanini tadqiq qilingan. Ushbu roman "Moghul Empire" roman-epopeyasining 1-kitobidir. Ushbu asar Zahiriddin Bobur Mirzo hayot yo'li, kechmishlariga bag'ishlanadi. Biz bu asarni o'rganish orqali ingliz yozuvchilari nazarida Bobur Mirzo shaxsiyati qay tarzda namoyon etilganligini aniqlashga harakat qildik.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur, Amir Temur, Humoyun Mirzo, Shayboniyxon, Xonzodabegim, Samarqand, Hindiston, roman-epopeya.*

**К ВОПРОСУ ОБ ОТНОШЕНИИ К ЛИЧНОСТИ ЗАХИРИДДИНА
БАБУРА В РОМАНЕ "НАЛЕТЫ С СЕВЕРА"**

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Аннотация. В данной диссертации исследуется роман “Налётчики с севера” известного английского писателя Алекса Рутхерфорда. Этот роман является первой книгой эпического романа “Империя Моголов”. Произведение посвящено жизни и приключениям Захириддина Бабура Мирзы. Изучая это произведение, мы попытались определить, как личность Бабура Мирзы проявилась в глазах английских писателей.

Ключевые слова: Захириддин Мухаммад Бабур, Амир Темур, Хумаюн Мирза, Шейбани-хан, Ханзодабегим, Самарканд, Индия, эпический роман.

Introduction. During our research, we were drawn to the epic novel “The Moghul Empire”, which consists of 6 books, covering the events from Babur Mirza’s accession to the throne, his founding of a great state in India, the era of the subsequent Baburids, to the overthrow of this dynasty by the British. It is also interesting that this book was created by the famous couple of writers Diana and Michael Preston, who used the common pseudonym Alex Rutherford for themselves. Below, we will consider how Zahiriddin is created as a character in the first book of this novel, “Raiders from the North,” dedicated to the history of Babur Mirza.

Analysis and results. In governing the state, Babur always tried to remember the teachings of his father and act based on the work “Temur tuzuklari” written by his great ancestor. With every action, he hopes to become a generation worthy of his great ancestors. His words when he was helpless in front of a strong opponent like Shaybani Khan are proof of this: “*Babur pressed his hands to the cold stone: “This is where Timur lies. When I first came to this place I promised that I would be worthy of him. The moment has come for me to fulfil that pledge. I’m going to lead out my men in one last stand before the city walls. Future generations will not be able to say that I yielded Timur’s city to a barbarian without a fight . . .”*¹ Babur, who captured Samarkand for the second time, although he was helpless as a result of the siege of Shaybani Khan, could not agree to surrender this city to the enemy without a fight. Knowing this, future generations felt a sense of reproach that they could call him a “coward”. The novelist tries to present Babur Mirzo to readers as a brave and noble person.

The main source that provides us with information about the life path of Zahiriddin Babur Mirzo is the autobiographical work “Baburnama” by Babur. It is also undeniable that historians and writers have relied on this book in the process of writing artistic, scientific and historical works. Alex Rutherford explains why Babur decided

¹ Alex Rutherford. Raiders from the North. – New York: St.Martin’s Press, 2010. – P. 190.
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to write this work: *“In a way . . . I want my future sons, and their sons after them, to know everything that happened to me – to know my achievements, my strengths – but I also want them to understand my mistakes . . . my failings . . . my thoughts . . . the choices I had to make to survive . . . From now on, I intend to record everything that happens – good or bad – frankly and honestly . . .”*² Babur Mirza decided to write everything down so that future generations would know what he had gone through, feel how difficult his life path was, and draw the right conclusions from his mistakes. It is worth noting that the work “Baburnama” is valued as a unique encyclopedia that provides information about the history, geography, nature, flora and fauna, language and religion, construction and horticulture of Afghanistan and India in the 15th and 16th centuries.

How Babur managed to defeat Ibrahim Lodi’s army, which had a large number of soldiers and huge elephants, with his small number of warriors in a short time, amazes many to this day. Alex Rutherford explains this as follows: *“Until now, although I’ve long wished to make one, a full-scale attack on Hindustan was not possible. I had neither the numbers of men nor any special advantage. The rulers there are numerous and strong. Their overlord is the proud, arrogant Sultan Ibrahim Lodi of Delhi. To win Hindustan I must defeat his huge armies and his ranks of war elephants. But with these new weapons I now see how I can do it. I may not be destined to have a great empire like Timur’s in the lands of my birth but with your cannon and muskets I can surpass his raid over the Indus to Delhi. We will fulfil the dreams we had all those years ago”*.³ According to the writer, Babur himself experienced a lot of fear and anxiety before the battle began. But later, with the help of modern weapons, cannons, and military tricks, he became confident that he would defeat the Indian soldiers equipped with old-fashioned weapons. Most importantly, Babur’s desire to establish a “Great State” like his ancestor Amir Temur prompted him to take a bold step.

Babur Mirza had 4 sons from different wives, they are Humayun Mirza, Kamran Mirza, Askari Mirza and Hindal Mirza. But among them, Humayun Mirza was especially loved, because he was the son of Babur’s beloved wife, Mohim Begum. In the novel “Raiders from the North”, Babur’s sincere feelings of adoration towards Humayun Mirza are expressed in his own words: *“If Humayun died it would also be an overwhelming personal loss – he had become closer to Humayun than to any of his other sons – but it would be something more too. It would be God’s way of saying that everything Babur had striven for, everything he had achieved, had been for nothing . .*

² Alex Rutherford. Raiders from the North. – New York: St.Martin’s Press, 2010. – P. 248.

³ Alex Rutherford. Raiders from the North. – New York: St.Martin’s Press, 2010. – P. 331.

. that he would never found an empire or a dynasty to prosper in Hindustan . . . that he should never have come – or, at the very least, not tried to outdo Timur by staying on. He should have been less proud, less blown up with vanity, and contented himself with his mountainous lands beyond the Khyber Pass”.⁴ Babur said that he would found a new state only for his son Humayun Mirza and his future descendants. He would fight against fierce enemies only so that his children could live a better life in the future. He would suffer greatly, especially when his beloved son Humayun Mirza was suffering from illness. Losing his son would have been a real disaster for Babur Mirza. The story of Babur, who was ready to sacrifice his own life in exchange for his son's life, has been celebrated for centuries as a symbol of the boundless love of a father for his son.

Conclusion. While reading the first book of the novel, a desire arose to get acquainted with the works about the representatives of the later Babur dynasty. The literary skills of the writers, the skillful use of various artistic methods will surely increase the interest of the readers. In our future studies, we will certainly study the subsequent parts of the novel.

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⁴ Alex Rutherford. Raiders from the North. – New York: St.Martin’s Press, 2010. – P. 420.
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